

In the above graph, patients whose initial COVID event coincided with a hospitalization are shown in green, while ED or outpatient visits are shown in magenta, reflecting the overall increased risk of developing PASC in hospitalized patients.

Overlaid near the x-axis are colored bar indicators of the approximate time periods that the alpha, delta and omicron viral variants became dominant in the US. We can see an initial spike in PASC, which is possibly related to the increased severity of disease and different treatment regimens experienced by patients in the early phase of the pandemic ([Bennett et al. 2021](#)). Current data is too early to describe PASC from omicron infections, however there is a slight trend towards increasing rates of PASC in recent months that coincide with the delta variant.

Limitations and Future work:

- The major limitation of these data continues to be the modest size of the training set defining the model of PASC. Training labels (long-covid clinic usage) come from four of the 69 sites considered in this analysis. As such, there are considerable heterogeneity issues between sites that will require further attention as more data become available. Future work will consider other training labels such as the emerging U09.9 diagnosis code.
- At the state level, we are limited in some capacity by sites which contribute data to N3C. To avoid conclusions drawn from small populations, we have censored some states that have few patients.
- For timeline data, we are limited in our ability to label PASC in recently-infected patients who do not yet have enough follow-up data to represent a post-acute infection period.
- These data represent a sample-of-convenience and are not meant to fully represent population dynamics within the US.

- 1 Pfaff ER, Girvin AT, Bennett TD, Bhatia A, Brooks IM, Deer RR, *et al.* Who has long-COVID? A big data approach n.d. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.10.18.21265168>.
- 2 Bennett TD, Moffitt RA, Hajagos JG, Amor B, Anand A, Bissell MM, *et al.* Clinical Characterization and Prediction of Clinical Severity of SARS-CoV-2 Infection Among US

RECOVER-N3C Q1 Queries
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Adults Using Data From the US National COVID Cohort Collaborative. *JAMA Network Open* 2021;4:e2116901–e2116901.

- 3 Pfaff ER, Girvin AT, Gabriel DL, Kostka K, Morris M, Palchuk M, *et al.* Synergies between centralized and federated approaches to data quality: A report from the National COVID Cohort Collaborative. *J Am Med Inform Assoc* 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocab217>.